

IMPACT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON THE DAILY ROUTINES AND SOCIAL LIVES OF FEMALE STUDENTS IN SPLIT (CROATIA): SOCIOLOGICAL RESEARCH

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Abstract

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 had a profound impact on people's lives, fundamentally altering daily routines, lifestyles, and social interactions. The rapid spread of the virus led to widespread lockdowns, including in Croatia, which temporarily halted in-person social activities. The introduction of preventive measures triggered significant changes in people's behaviors, resulting in disruptions to their regular routines.

As social beings, humans rely on close interpersonal connections, especially in times of crisis. However, the COVID-19 pandemic imposed social distancing and fostered feelings of fear and uncertainty. These changes affect individuals of all ages, contributing to elevated stress levels. The pandemic also left a significant mark on the education system, with universities shifting to exclusively online classes during this period. Given these circumstances, the aim of this paper is to explore how students coped during the lockdown. The research questions addressed their views on isolation measures, the recommendations from the national health authorities, their interpersonal relationships (communication and interactions), daily routines, and stress levels. This study presents findings from research conducted in 2020 during the lockdown, which was based on semi-structured interviews with a sample of eleven female students from the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences in Split (Croatia).

The results show that all participants complied with the isolation measures and regarded them as appropriate. Most maintained communication with friends through video calls, primarily on WhatsApp, although other social media platforms, such as Instagram and Facebook, were also used. Those who ventured outside during the lockdown most often took walks in nature, ensuring that they maintained the recommended physical distance from others. Many participants reported that their relationships with their partners remained unchanged, whereas their relationships with their parents, whom most of them lived with, actually improved. During the isolation period, participants noted healthier eating habits, increased physical activity, more sleep, and greater consumption of TV shows, movies, and books than usual. However, most also experienced heightened stress levels, particularly at the onset of the lockdown due to uncertainty and fear, although these levels gradually decreased over time.

Keywords: COVID-19 pandemic, Lockdown, Female students, Croatia, Social life, Daily routine.

1 INTRODUCTION

Humans are inherently social beings, and one of our primary needs is to belong to and live within a community. This need becomes even more pronounced during times of crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic,

which swept the world in 2020, dramatically altered people's lives and highlighted the importance of this social connection. Rather than fostering close social ties, the pandemic enforced social distancing, which led to mutual separation and significant changes in social functioning.

The crisis caused by the coronavirus is not just something "out there"; it becomes part of our social reality through its symbolic dimensions (Pfister, 2020). The pandemic's widespread closure of social activities and the shift to digital communication disrupted the normal social routines that formed the foundation of social reality. These disruptions have the potential to impact our sense of ontological security, which, when compromised, can contribute to heightened anxiety. Ontological security is vital for our daily functioning (Paska, 2021), and according to Giddens (1991), it refers to the sense of stability and continuity that individuals experience, which is closely linked to routine behaviors. As Giddens (1984: 282) noted, a routine is "psychologically linked to the minimization of unconscious sources of anxiety." Furthermore, "routinized practices are the prime expression of the duality of structure in respect of the continuity of social life" (Giddens 1984: 282). Routines, therefore, are essential in maintaining the continuity of social life, especially in times of crisis, when people's safety and security are threatened. They not only are a form of structure imposed from above but also provide rhythm, predictability, order, and control to our lives (Highmore, 2004).

The coronavirus pandemic disrupted daily routines, lifestyles, and social interactions. Lockdowns were imposed across the globe, including in Croatia, which meant that in-person socializing ceased for extended periods. The preventive measures taken resulted in shifts in people's behavioral patterns, further disrupting their daily routines. The pandemic itself triggered fear and uncertainty in society, deeply affecting public behavior. These changes in people's lives have caused additional stress and posed a threat to mental health. Humans seek ways to reduce stress when faced with challenging circumstances, and individuals often resort to various strategies, some of which may not be effective (Muslić, 2020). However, uncertainty about new risks, such as COVID-19, only increases anxiety (Muslić, 2020). This period of self-isolation, lockdowns, and border closures is expected to have lasting psychological effects (Reddy, 2020), such as anxiety, due to a lack of social contact and a reduced ability to manage stress (Grujić et al., 2020).

Sociologists have long expressed concern over the weakening of the family unit, with family members becoming increasingly distant, communicating less, and trusting each other less (Giddens, 1984). However, some researchers argue that the pandemic, by forcing people to stay and work at home, may have brought family members closer together—although these changes have been relatively small and limited (Verma & Prakash, 2020).

The pandemic also had a profound impact on the education system. In Croatia, university courses were conducted exclusively online during this period. For children and adolescents, being confined at home due to online schooling led to feelings of uncertainty and anxiety. Studies have shown that 91% of the global student population is negatively affected by the closure of universities (Lee et al., 2020). Furthermore, the pandemic has posed particular risks to women's mental health (Flynn et al., 2020). These factors make it crucial to explore how individuals, especially female students, experienced this period, how they interacted with others, their daily routines, and how they spent their leisure time.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Aim and Research Questions

The general aim of this qualitative study was to explore how female students at the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences in Split (Croatia) coped during the lockdown. In qualitative research, the role of the researcher is to gain an in depth, intensive, and comprehensive understanding of the context being studied (Gray, 2009). This is achieved through the formulation of well-defined and focused research questions, which lie at the heart of qualitative inquiry (Maxwell, 2005). Research questions provide the necessary framework to guide the investigation and ensure focus throughout the study (Creswell, 2003).

This study investigates two central themes and several associated categories: communication and interaction with friends/partners with respect to isolation measures imposed during the lockdown and participants' daily routines during this period.

To guide this exploration, the following research questions were posed:

1. What are the students' views on isolation measures?
2. How did they respond to the national headquarters measures?

3. How did they maintain communication with friends and partners during the lockdown?
4. Did they have in-person meetings with friends or partners?
5. How did their relationships with their parents evolve during this period?
6. What did their daily routines look like during the lockdown?
7. Did they experience feelings of worry or stress?

2.2 Sample Size

In qualitative research, determining an adequate sample size is often driven by the principle of saturation—the point at which the inclusion of additional participants no longer yields new insights. Although there is no strict rule for the number of participants required to achieve data saturation, Hennink, Kaiser, and Marconi (2016) suggest that nine interviews are typically sufficient to reach code saturation, where no new themes emerge from the data. In this study, 11 participants were interviewed.

2.3 Research Participants

Given the focus on female students, purposive sampling was employed to select participants. The final sample consisted of 11 female students aged 20--26 years who were interviewed during the lockdown period. Seven of the participants lived with their parents, two lived with both their parents and a partner, one lived with her husband and child, and one lived alone. Housing arrangements varied: six students lived in apartments, four in houses, and one in a student dormitory. With respect to relationship status, three participants were in a relationship, one was married, and seven were single.

2.4 Research Procedure

The research was conducted in 2020 during the COVID-19 lockdown, utilizing semi-structured interviews carried out online via WhatsApp video calls or Skype. This approach was necessitated by the inability to conduct in-person interviews. On average, the interviews lasted approximately 20 minutes.

Prior to each interview, participants were thoroughly briefed on the study's objectives, the methodology, and the voluntary nature of their participation. They were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without providing an explanation and that they would have access to the interview transcripts to review their responses. The participants provided written informed consent for the audio recording of the interviews and for the subsequent use of the data for analysis, with assurances of confidentiality. Each participant was assigned a code name (e.g., P1, P2, etc.) to ensure anonymity.

The interviews were recorded via a mobile audio recording application, and the recordings were transcribed verbatim. The transcriptions were then analyzed in detail to identify portions of the interviews that addressed the research questions. A coding approach was employed, where themes and subthemes that emerged from the analysis of the transcripts were used as codes. The participants' statements were categorized and coded according to their relevance to the research questions, with attention given to the interrelationship between codes, categories, and the broader research context.

Data analysis combines both deductive and inductive approaches. The deductive approach was guided by specific questions derived from an existing conceptual framework (e.g., isolation measures, communication patterns, daily routines). In contrast, the inductive approach allowed for the development of new categories on the basis of the participants' responses. This approach involved "building" predefined categories from the specific observations of the participants (e.g., regarding their personal use of cigarettes, alcohol, and opiates), thereby generating new insights and codes that had not been anticipated in the initial framework. The final phase of the analysis involved interpretation of the findings, which provided a comprehensive understanding of how female students experienced and coped during the lockdown.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Communication and Interaction

According to the survey results, all participants agreed that the preventive measures implemented by national headquarters were appropriate:

I think the measures were good, and some decisions were made in a timely manner. (P2)

I believe they were effective, as the infection rate was reduced. On the first day of the curfew, I was

sitting with a friend outside, and the police patrol circulated, asking people to leave public spaces (including us). Since then, I haven't left home for a month. (P8)

The measures were correct because, without quarantine, too many people would have become infected, and our healthcare system would not have been able to manage the situation. A scenario such as Italy's, where we would have had to make choices about who would live and who would not, could have happened. Staying home was the least we could do for a better future. (P4)

The government did an excellent job considering the extraordinary and difficult nature of the situation. (P9)

The measures were well thought out, and I fully agree with the decisions made by the national headquarters. (P10)

Most participants adhered to the recommendations of the national headquarters during the lockdown and refrained from meeting with friends in person:

From the start of quarantine until recently, I strictly followed all the measures and was completely isolated. (P7)

I followed all the measures, and I believe this was key to keeping my family safe from infection. (P11)

I did not meet many friends, especially during the first week of isolation. Later, I started walking with one friend but kept contacts minimal. (P10)

Those who went outside during the lockdown often did so in nature, ensuring that they maintained the recommended physical distance:

I was mostly outdoors with my friends and my dog, for about an hour or two each day. (P6)

There were no more than three of us at a time, so we stayed outdoors and kept our distance. (P3)

Most participants stayed in touch with friends primarily through video calls, most often via WhatsApp, although they also used other social networks, such as Instagram and Facebook:

Communication moved to virtual platforms, but it was about the same as before. (P11)

I kept in touch with friends via social networks such as WhatsApp, platforms, and occasionally with some in-person socializing. (P8)

This is accomplished via video calls, regular calls, and WhatsApp. (P4)

As the measures became more lenient, participants began to socialize in person again but with a smaller circle of people:

For the first two weeks, I was at a weekend house and only communicated with my family. When I returned to Split, I did not see anyone for another week. After three weeks of isolation, I started meeting friends outdoors. (P3)

At first, not for the first month, but later, I started sitting on benches in front of the house or walking the dog, visiting friends' apartments, etc. (P8)

Only in the last two or three weeks did I start physically socializing with friends, but I still try to minimize contact with as many people as possible and maintain physical distance. (P4)

However, those participants who were in relationships during the lockdown (three of them) remained physically close to their partners and continued intimate relationships despite the restrictions. Two participants stated that their relationships with their partners did not change during this period, whereas one reported some changes:

The daily routine was very different from normal, which led to occasional friction, but nothing serious or concerning. (P2)

Since most participants (nine of them) lived with their parents during the lockdown, it was interesting to determine whether their relationships with them had changed. All the participants reported that their relationships with their parents improved during the period of isolation:

My relationship with my mother improved because she did not have to work and had more time to

relax and focus on her hobbies and things that made her happy. (P3)

Our relationship was excellent—we used the time to bond and take walks in nature together. (P9)

In some ways, our relationship was even better because there was no hectic lifestyle that would cause arguments. (P11)

Spending more time together allowed us to get to know each other better, and our relationship even improved. (P7)

For those whose relationships with their parents were strained, the reasons given were as follows:

There were arguments because my brother, sister, and I were all dealing with schoolwork and feeling stressed. (P5)

At first, we argued a lot, mostly over trivial things such as washing dishes. The real reason, however, was that we were all frustrated and unaccustomed to being at home together all the time. (P10)

3.2 Daily Routines

Given the confinement at home, it was intriguing to explore how the participants' daily routines were affected—how they ate, whether they exercised, how much they slept, and what activities they engaged in. The data revealed that all the participants were healthier during the isolation period:

The quantity but not the quality of food did not change. With the suspension of work and live classes, I stopped eating fast food and bakery products during breaks or after shifts. (P4)

I ate healthier foods, including more fruits and vegetables. (P10)

We ate better quality meals, as I usually take over cooking on weekdays, and it is often quick lunches. With more time, my mother could focus more on nutrition. (P7)

Eight participants reported exercising more than usual during the lockdown:

Yes, I exercised for approximately 30 days, three times a week. The fitness sessions were live on Instagram, and I followed them in my room at the student dormitory. (P8)

I did home workouts, ran, and walked. (P2)

I did small home workouts. (P10)

I practiced yoga via the Zoom app. (P6)

Yes, I exercised in my apartment using an exercise app on my phone. (P4)

Additionally, nine participants stated that they slept more than usual during this period:

I slept more. I woke up later since I didn't have to get up early like I used to. (P8)

I tried to establish a routine and get up at the same time every day, but I often got carried away and slept longer than planned. (P7)

All the participants reported watching more movies and series than usual did, and some (five participants) also read more books, played games, and played cards:

I had more free time, so I watched more films and series. I also bought a PlayStation, so I played games. (P3)

During isolation, I watched more films and series than usual. I also read more for college because we had more assignments. (P8)

I read more books since I usually enjoy reading a good book, and I took advantage of the extra time. (P11)

We played cards every other night and watched movies together. (P7)

With respect to vice, five participants did not smoke or consume alcohol. Four stated that their consumption of cigarettes and alcohol remained unchanged during the lockdown, whereas two participants reported using these substances more than before. However, most participants (eight) indicated an increase in stress levels, especially at the start of the lockdown, due to uncertainty and fear. Fortunately, these feelings

subsided over time:

At first, I was stressed, anxious, and worried because everything was new, and suddenly, all my daily activities and habits were prohibited. However, as time passed, these feelings diminished. (P4)

Yes, I was anxious and stressed both because of the situation we found ourselves in and the uncertainty about what would happen afterward. (P9)

At the beginning, I was a little stressed because of the unfamiliar situation and the uncertainty about how things would develop. I worried about my loved ones, especially those in high-risk groups, and about what would happen with classes. Over time, my anxiety decreased because I saw that the faculty was understanding of the emergency and that my loved ones and I followed all the necessary instructions. (P11)

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted the daily lives of people worldwide, including in Croatia. These changes primarily affect daily routines, communication patterns, and interactions with friends, ultimately influencing both lifestyle and stress levels. To curb the spread of the virus, a lockdown was implemented, disrupting established routines. The research for this paper was conducted during the lockdown and focused on a sample of female students from the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences in Split, Croatia.

The findings reveal that all participants followed the isolation measures set by national authorities and viewed them as necessary. Most participants stayed in touch with friends through video calls, particularly on WhatsApp, while also using other social media platforms, such as Instagram and Facebook. Those who ventured outside during the lockdown typically walked in nature, maintaining the recommended physical distance from others.

Interestingly, the participants reported that their relationships with their partners remained unchanged and that their relationships with their parents—whom most of the participants were living with at the time—actually improved. During the isolation period, the participants tended to be healthier, exercise more, sleep longer, watch more TV shows and films, and read more books than usual. However, despite these positive lifestyle changes, many participants experienced heightened stress levels, particularly at the beginning of the lockdown, due to uncertainty and fear. Fortunately, this stress gradually diminished over time.

REFERENCE LIST

- Creswell, J. W. (2003). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches. Second Edition*. Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi: SAGE Publications.
- Flynn, R., Riches, E., Reid, G., Rosenberg, S., & Niedzwiedz, C. (2020). *Rapid review of the impact of COVID-19 on mental health*. Edinburgh: Public Health Scotland.
- Giddens, A. (1991). *Modernity and Self-identity*. London: Polity Press.
- Giddens, A. (1984). *The Constitution of Society. Outline of the Theory of Structuration*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Giddens, A. (1994). *The Transformation of Intimacy*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Gray, D. E. (2009). *Doing Research in the Real World. Second Edition*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Grujičić, R., Bogdanović, J., Stupar, S., Maslak, J., & Pejović-Milovančević, M. (2020). COVID-19 pandemija - uticaj na decu i mlade. *Psihijatrija danas*, 52(1-2): 99-111. <https://doi.org/10.5937/PsihDan2001099G>
- Hennink, M. M., Kaiser, B. N., & Marconi, V.C. (2016). Code saturation versus meaning saturation: How many interviews are enough? *Qualitative Health Research*, 27(4): 591–608. <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973231666653>
- Highmore, B. (2004). Homework: Routine, Social Aesthetics and The Ambiguity of Everyday Life. *Cultural Studies*, 18(2–3): 306–327. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950238042000201536>

- Lee, P. I., Hu, Y. L., Chen, P. Y., Huang, Y. C., & Hsueh, P. R. (2020). Are children less susceptible to COVID-19? *Journal of Microbiology, Immunology, and Infection*, 53(3), 371–372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmii>.
- Maxwell, J. A. (2005). *Qualitative Research Design: An Interactive Approach. Second Edition. Applied Social Research Methods Series, Vol. 41*. Thousand Oaks, London, New Delhi: SAGE Publications.
- Muslić, Lj. (2020). Koronavirus kao prijetnja mentalnom zdravlju. In Bogdan, A. et al. (Eds). *Koronavirus i mentalno zdravlje: psihološki aspekti, savjeti i preporuke*. Zagreb: Hrvatska psihološka komora. pp. 13-17.
- Paska, I. (2021). Bits and Pieces: Experiences of Social Reality in the Midst of the Covid-19 Pandemic. *In medias res*, 10(18): 2789-2802. <https://doi.org/10.46640/imr.10.18.1>
- Pfister, S. M. (2020). Theorizing – the Social Definition of the Corona Pandemic. *The European Sociologist, Pandemic (im)Possibilities*, 1(45).
- Reddy, V. (2020). More eyes on COVID-19: Perspectives from Sociology - The social life of a virus. *South African Journal of Science*, 116 (7-8). <https://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2020/8496>
- Verma, A.K., & Prakash, S. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 on Environment and Society. *Journal of Global Biosciences*, 9(5): 7352-7363.